

Neutrinoless double-beta decay: UK community strategy

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Strategy Summary

The observation of neutrinoless double-beta decay (NDBD) would constitute a landmark discovery in particle physics, setting the foundations for the development of a long-sought theory of fermion masses and the explanation for why our universe contains more matter than antimatter.

Over the last 20 years, the UK community has pursued a multi-pronged experimental approach to discover NDBD, which has enabled the UK to act as a driving force in the field, with recognised intellectual leadership. This document summarises the UK NDBD community's strategy for the near- (<5 years), medium- (5-15 years) and long-term (>15 years) future.

The strategy can be summarised in four points:

- 1) Continued support for the exploitation of LEGEND-200, SNO+ and the SuperNEMO Demonstrator, recognising the unique near-term physics programmes of each experiment and building on substantial prior UK investment.
- 2) Support the construction of LEGEND-1000 in the near term as the highest priority project in the USA and Europe, ensuring UK leadership in an experiment that will have $> 3\sigma$ discovery sensitivity for Majorana neutrinos in the inverted neutrino mass ordering range in the medium term.
- 3) Support the development and implementation of higher loading phases of SNO+, which will provide complementary sensitivity with a different isotope in the medium term and lay foundations for a technique that might be extended to the normal mass ordering in the longer term.
- 4) Exploit cross-field scientific and technological synergies with the XLZD dark matter community and explore strategic R&D opportunities offered by complementary technologies, such as NEXT, to further strengthen the main programme in the medium term, while continuing to support blue-skies R&D into new technologies able to reach sensitivities beyond the inverted mass ordering in the long term.

The rest of the document gives the background to this strategy in terms of the science case, international activities, funding landscape and the current UK programme.

Science Case

The observation of neutrinoless double-beta decay (NDBD) would constitute a landmark discovery in particle physics. This lepton-number-violating nuclear transition, which would result in the net creation of matter-particles (i.e., two leptons) without their balancing antiparticles, is predicted by leading theories to explain the mysterious origin of neutrino masses (which is not accounted for in the Standard Model)

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and the matter-antimatter asymmetry in our universe. If observed, NDBD would prove that neutrinos and antineutrinos are two sides of the same coin, offering a bridge between matter and antimatter. Furthermore, it would establish that the Standard Model's last global symmetry, B-L, is not conserved, bringing us closer to comprehending the fundamental laws and symmetries of physics.

We currently find ourselves at a pivotal moment for NDBD searches. Over the past few decades, various technologies have been developed and tested through large-scale experiments. This has laid the groundwork for the selection of the most promising concepts to begin exploring some of the most relevant regions of parameter space. A theoretical lower limit exists on the NDBD rate if the process is mediated by neutrinos with masses following the inverted ordering (IO). Such a limit would correspond to an effective Majorana mass of ~ 18 meV, which falls into the sensitivity range being targeted by the next generation of NDBD experiments. If, on the other hand, neutrino masses obey a "normal ordering" (NO), then the rate of the process can be lower than the IO limit, and the detection of NDBD could thus require more sensitive approaches, for which the next generation of experiments is a necessary stepping stone. Furthermore, the fact remains that the nature of the neutrino mass mechanism and lepton number conservation is not understood and, as such, surprises may well await, as they often have in the history of neutrino physics. Hence, NDBD is an extremely fertile area of research with significant discovery potential, and the hunt for NDBD should thus be regarded as an open search for new physics, similar to the hunt for physics beyond the Standard Model at the LHC.

This is an extremely challenging experimental endeavour. In such a rare event search, it is crucial to attain sufficiently low background levels that are well understood, and to be able to identify and deal with unexpected backgrounds. The various detection techniques have different ways of approaching this, which also makes the use of different experimental methods important for verification. Furthermore, in addition to uncertainties for the relevant neutrino mass range, there exist theoretical uncertainties regarding the nuclear matrix elements that determine NDBD decay rates of different isotopes. As such, the required sensitivity and best choice of isotope is not entirely obvious, with different models favouring different isotopes to varying degrees. Given the gravity of the potential scientific impact, a discovery of NDBD would therefore almost certainly require confirmation by more than one isotope and/or detection method. As a result of all this, the importance of tackling the problem with different isotopes and cultivating a variety of approaches for both near-term and long-term experiments is well recognised by the worldwide community. Thus, while current and upcoming experiments are exploring uncharted parameter space, ongoing blue-skies research and development need to be simultaneously pushed forward to achieve sensitivities beyond the next generation of instruments.

The pursuit of NDBD forms an important part of a coherent UK neutrino programme, together with the current and planned neutrino oscillation experiments, experiments measuring the electron neutrino mass, and cosmological surveys. In the next couple of decades, this programme will lead us to establish the neutrino nature, the ordering and value of its mass eigenstates, and the extent of CP-violation in the neutrino sector.

International Activities and Funding

The high priority of the NDBD programme in international particle and nuclear physics roadmaps on the one hand, and the recognition of significant costs of the upcoming experiments on the other, have led to increased coordination of the international effort in this area. As a result, a number of summits and reviews have taken place over the past several years in Europe and North America, such as the US DOE Portfolio Review in 2021 and the Astroparticle Physics European Consortium (APPEC) strategy update. These reviews identified three leading contenders for the next step of the international NDBD programme to build "tonne-scale" experiments to fully explore the IO parameter space: CUPID, LEGEND-1000 and nEXO. While the US DOE process identified LEGEND-1000 as the top-ranked project, it was agreed that conducting all three experiments would enrich the field. The international stakeholders in NDBD research agreed to create a working group to find the most efficient way to fund all three experiments, thus "maximising the chances of a Nobel prize calibre discovery".

Elsewhere, other important high-profile efforts are underway providing complementarity and identifying future pathways to even more sensitive future experiments. The Japanese project KamLAND-Zen is using

liquid scintillator loaded with NDBD isotope and currently provides one of the most stringent limits on the Majorana neutrino mass. An upgrade of KamLAND-Zen is being planned to probe further into the IO parameter space. In Canada, the SNO+ project is pioneering a similar approach but based on a different isotope, which has the advantage of not requiring expensive isotopical enrichment, and could therefore allow for a substantial up-scaling of the isotope mass and experimental sensitivity. Another European project, NEXT, is exploring the use of tracking in high-pressure time-projection chambers (TPC) and methods to identify the NDBD daughter isotope, potentially a background-free technique able to reach sensitivities beyond the IO.

In addition, the proposed XLZD dark matter experiment offers an opportunity for cross-disciplinary complementary measurements in the IO region using a liquid dual-phase time projection chamber.

The Current UK Programme

UK research groups are pursuing a broad NDBD programme that employs a range of approaches and isotopes. They have historically played a major leadership role in preparing, constructing, and commissioning the SNO+ and SuperNEMO Demonstrator experiments, which are in or about to enter the exploitation phase, reaching world-leading sensitivities in NDBD in ^{130}Te and ^{82}Se , respectively.

SuperNEMO, in particular, will investigate nuclear physics behind NDBD, and search for evidence of exotic decays. It serves as a proof of concept of a technique to explore the NDBD mechanism in the event of a discovery.

In the last few years, the UK has also established strong participation and a leading position in ^{76}Ge NDBD searches through the exploitation of LEGEND-200, which started physics data taking in March 2023, and the preparation of LEGEND-1000, the tonne-scale experiment prioritised by the US Department of Energy. LEGEND-200 will transition to LEGEND-1000 towards the end of this decade, reaching by the end of the next one a $>3\sigma$ discovery capability in the entire IO parameter space. The UK particle and nuclear physics communities play leading roles in the physics exploitation of LEGEND-200 and the design of LEGEND-1000 exploiting their established strengths in cryogenic systems, high-purity germanium detector characterisation, radiopurity assays and core software development.

SNO+ builds on the success of the SNO experiment, now using liquid scintillator that can be loaded with large masses of tellurium. The concept originated in the UK and utilises natural tellurium, which contains 34% of the isotope of interest (^{130}Te), hence avoiding the need for enrichment. The initial 0.5% Te loading is scheduled to be introduced to the detector in 2025. Recent further advances in the loading technique developed by the Oxford group could lead to an increase in the loading by a factor of ~ 5 , providing high sensitivity to the IO parameter space in the medium term with an isotope different from LEGEND. In the longer term, such an approach may provide a promising way of achieving sensitivity well beyond the IO, to the non-degenerate NO region. The detector technology also allows for a substantial diverse programme of other physics, including solar, geo, reactor and supernova neutrinos

New opportunities to further enrich the UK NDBD programme have recently emerged from the strong UK and international support to build the XLZD liquid-xenon rare-event observatory for dark-matter and neutrino physics, including the prospect of hosting the experiment at the Boulby Underground Laboratory. While mainly targeted at dark matter, XLZD could also measure NDBD in the IO range for ^{136}Xe , further bolstering the main programme. Additionally, major synergies have been identified in the areas of radioassay and clean construction techniques with the other UK NDBD experiments, which would further elevate the role of the UK in the international context.

The UK currently also has involvement via an ERC grant in the construction and assembly of NEXT-100, a detector that will demonstrate the scalability of the high-pressure TPC technology, and is planned to start taking data in early 2024.

Finally, world-leading technology R&D for searches beyond the IO parameter space is also being pursued in the UK. There is a strong effort in the area of loaded liquid scintillators leveraging on the expertise developed by the UK groups for SNO+, large HPGe detectors with alternative electrode schemes, as well as xenon TPC and barium tagging being developed in the context of the NEXT experiment.